

Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with N^1, N^3 -Bis(2,4-dinitrophenyl)diethylenetriamine, N^1, N^4 -Bis(2,4-dinitrophenyl)triethylenetetramine and the corresponding 2,4-Diaminophenyl Derivatives

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N^1, N^3 -Bis(2,4-dinitrophenyl)diethylenetriamine (L_1), N^1, N^4 -bis(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-triethylenetetramine (L_2) and the corresponding 2,4-diaminophenyl substituted derivatives (L_3) and (L_4) form 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 metal-ligand complexes with Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} of the type $[M(L_1)_2]X_2$ or Y ; $[M(L_2)X_2]$ and $[M(L_3 \text{ or } L_4)X_2]$, where $M = Cu^{II}$ or Ni^{II} ; $X = Cl^-$, CH_3COO^- or SCN^- ; $Y = SO_4^{2-}$. The complexes have been characterised by elemental analyses, conductance, magnetic, and ir and uv spectral studies.

A large number of transition metal complexes containing multidentate nitrogen donors exhibiting a variety of structures have been prepared and studied previously^{1,2}. In the present paper we report the synthesis and characterisation of some new complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with the ligands N^1, N^3 -bis(2,4-dinitrophenyl)diethylenetriamine (L_1), N^1, N^4 -bis(2,4-dinitrophenyl)triethylenetetramine (L_2) and the corresponding 2,4-diaminophenyl substituted derivatives (L_3) and (L_4), respectively.

Experimental

N^1, N^3 -Bis(2,4-dinitrophenyl)diethylenetriamine, N^1, N^4 -bis(2,4-dinitrophenyl)triethylenetetramine : Diethylenetriamine (1.03 ml, 0.01 mol) or triethylenetetramine (2.00 ml, 0.01 mol) were dissolved in ethanol (25 ml) and refluxed with 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (4.7 g, 0.02 mol) for 5 h. The ligands were crystallised out from the resulting yellow solu-

tion as yellow needles using ether, and recrystallised with hot ethanol.

For the preparation of ligands N^1, N^3 -bis(2,4-diaminophenyl)diethylenetriamine (L_3) and N^1, N^4 -bis(2,4-diaminophenyl)triethylenetetramine (L_4), the nitro ligands were dissolved in methanol, treated with Raney nickel (0.5 g) and refluxed on a water bath. The required amount of hydrazine hydrate was then added dropwise till the reduction was complete and the reduction product was separated by precipitating out the amine-hydrochloride as white solid which was recrystallised from hot ethanol (Table 1).

Preparation of complexes : The complexes were prepared by treating 0.01 mol of metal(II) salt with 0.02 mol of the ligand L_1 or 0.01 mol of the ligands L_2 , L_3 or L_4 in methanol and refluxing the solution for 2 h. The reaction product mixture was run over tlc plates and the complexes were separated by repeated crystallisation using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°).

The complexes were found to be insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMF and MeCN and stable upto 250°. The analytical, conductance and magnetic data are given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

In the structure of the two ligands L_1 and L_2 , the condensation of amines with 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene to occur only at the terminal NH_2 groups while the secondary NH remains unaffected. This

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF LIGANDS

Ligand	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	Ir band (cm ⁻¹)				Nmr bands (τ)	
	C	H	N		ν_{NH} ν_{NH_2}	ν_{as}	ν_{s} NO ₂	ν_{as} NO ₂	NH protons	Phenyl protons
L ₁	44.50 (44.13)	4.10 (3.90)	22.10 (22.52)	420 (435)	3 260mbr 3 160sbr	1 600m 1 590m 1 560w	1 426s	1 323s	8.2	1.58
L ₂	45.65 (45.18)	4.58 (4.18)	23.08 (23.43)	452 (478)	3 230mbr 3 210w	1 605m 1 507s 1 520m 1 480m	1 425vs	1 320s	8.32	1.62
L ₃	62.52 (62.82)	7.65 (7.93)	31.40 (31.11)	308 (315)	3 220vs } _{db} 3 300s } _{db}	1 610 - 1 605sdb 1 570s 1 510w 1 480m	—	—	—	1.54
L ₄	60.05 (60.33)	8.21 (8.37)	31.52 (31.28)	352 (358)	3 320vs 3 280s	1 600w 1 560m 1 480m	—	—	—	1.62

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.	λ_{M}^{**} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		M	N	X		
[Cu(L ₁) ₂]Cl ₂	Yellowish green	6.61 (6.32)	19.02 (19.54)	6.86 (7.06)	1.80	162.3 ^a
[Cu(L ₁) ₂]SO ₄	Greenish yellow	6.53 (6.16)	19.28 (19.03)	9.76 (9.32)	1.91	256.6 ^b
[Ni(L ₁) ₂]Cl ₂	Dark yellow	6.52 (6.60)	17.49 (18.85)	7.50 (7.12)	3.32	158.4 ^a
[Ni(L ₁) ₂]SO ₄	Yellow	5.72 (5.60)	19.11 (19.62)	9.65 (9.39)	3.02	248.3 ^b
[Cu(L ₂)Cl ₂]	Greenish yellow	10.58 (10.10)	18.28 (18.00)	10.99 (11.59)	1.85	20.4 ^a
[Cu(L ₂)(CH ₃ COO) ₂]	Brown	9.63 (9.24)	16.98 (16.59)	—	1.90	80.4 ^b
[Cu(L ₂)(NCS) ₂]	Brown	9.28 (9.65)	21.58 (21.29)	17.18 (17.64)	1.99	28.6 ^a
[Ni(L ₂)Cl ₂]	Greenish yellow	9.64 (9.00)	18.43 (17.93)	11.34 (11.74)	3.20	18.4 ^b
[Ni(L ₂)(CH ₃ COO) ₂]	Brown	8.95 (8.49)	17.10 (16.58)	—	3.42	38.8 ^a
[Ni(L ₂)(NCS) ₂]	Brown	8.38 (8.97)	21.69 (21.45)	17.90 (18.10)	2.99	69.6 ^b
[Ni(L ₂)(CH ₃ COO) ₂]	Brown	12.50 (12.78)	19.28 (19.73)	—	0.75	141.4 ^a
[Ni(L ₃)Cl ₂]	Pink	13.50 (13.18)	22.51 (22.04)	16.65 (16.07)	0.67	241.6 ^b
[Cu(L ₄)Cl ₂]	Brown	12.50 (12.89)	22.18 (22.74)	14.05 (14.41)	1.89	152.3 ^a
[Cu(L ₄)SO ₄]	Brown	12.50 (12.27)	21.33 (21.64)	18.28 (18.55)	2.06	238.4 ^b
[Ni(L ₄)Cl ₂]	Pink	12.58 (12.04)	22.65 (22.96)	14.21 (14.56)	3.28	148.3 ^a
[Ni(L ₄)SO ₄]	Violet	11.93 (11.43)	21.41 (21.84)	19.15 (18.72)	3.29	243.6 ^b

*L₁=C₁₀H₁₇N₇O₈, L₂=C₁₀H₂₂N₆O₈, L₃=C₁₀H₂₂N₇, L₄=C₁₀H₂₀N₆. **In ^aDMF, ^bMeCN.

is confirmed by the presence of (i) NH stretch at 3 300 cm⁻¹, (ii) presence of only two types of protons, *i.e.* NH and aromatic at τ 8–9 and 1–2 with an integral ratio of 3 : 6 (L₁) and 4 : 6 (L₂), respectively, in the nmr spectra. However, the involvement of secondary NH will lead to the disappearance of NH stretch and will give an integral ratio of 2 : 9 and 4 : 12 for the two protons. The presence of free nitro groups is shown by two bands due to asymmetric and symmetric NO₂

stretch at 1 428 and 1 320 cm⁻¹. In the ir spectra of ligands L₂ and L₄ these bands disappear and instead a doublet appears at 3 300 cm⁻¹ confirming their reduced nature. These ligands (L₁–L₄) are thus expected to act as tri-(L₁), tetra-(L₂), penta-(L₃) or hexa-dentate (L₄), respectively, as supported by the 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 stoichiometry [M(L₁)₂]X₂ or Y, and [M(L)]X₂ or Y of the complexes, where M=Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}; X=Cl⁻, CH₃COO⁻ and SCN⁻; Y=SO₄²⁻; L=L₂, L₃ and L₄ (Table 2). The

coordination sites in case of L_1 and L_2 is the imine group alone, while for L_3 and L_4 , it is the imine as well as amino groups as evident from lowering of ν_{NH} band by 100 cm^{-1} and the appearance of a doublet at 3310 and 3280 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of the complexes^{3,4}. The nitro group vibrations remain unaffected in complexes showing their non-involvement in coordination.

The bands corresponding to N-bonded thiocyanate are observed at 2100 – 2040 cm^{-1} and those due to coordinated chlorogroups^{5,8} at 280 cm^{-1} . The M–N vibrations were observed in the form of weak bands in the range 430 – 500 cm^{-1} .

The room temperature (295 K) magnetic moments for all Cu^{II} complexes were between 1.70 and 1.90 B.M., which is indicative of the presence of one unpaired electron. The magnetic moments of the Ni^{II} complexes with L_1 , L_2 and L_4 were in the range 3.00–3.20 B.M., indicating their high-spin pseudooctahedral structure⁹. The Ni^{II} complexes with L_3 were low-spin (0.70 B.M.) and a square-pyramidal pentacoordinate structure seems most probable for these complexes due to the formation of a very stable five-membered ring open on the side around the metal center. The small temperature independent paramagnetism which appears to have developed on the ion is due to spin crossover involving steric deformation^{10,11}.

The electronic spectra of all the complexes have been recorded in solid state and those of Cu^{II} complexes show a very broad absorption maxima at 17000 cm^{-1} corresponding to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transition characteristic of distorted octahedral geometry^{12,13}. The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes show one band around 8500 cm^{-1} with shoulders on one or both the sides and two other bands around 15000 and 26000 cm^{-1} , assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions, respectively. The position of these bands is consistent with a pseudooctahedral environment around the ion¹⁴. In the electronic spectra of complexes of L_3 only charge transfer bands are seen as expected. These

spectra have been used for calculating the various ligand field parameters for different complexes. The Dq values are found to be very large (around 1400 cm^{-1} for Cu^{II} and 1050 cm^{-1} for Ni^{II} complexes) suggesting the presence of a strong metal–ligand bond in these complexes. The values of Racah parameter (B), nephelauxetic ratio (β) and spin-orbit coupling constant which are correspondingly in the range 822 – 979 cm^{-1} , 3.79 – 0.96 and -147.68 to 701.49 cm^{-1} further suggest a considerable degree of covalency or orbital overlap in the complexes^{15,16}.

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